

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Pilot Implementation

HerStory Map excursion Guidelines for Sofia (Bulgaria)

WP2 D2.2

HerStory Consortium

Amendment History

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1. Introduction

The current document is developed to provide guidelines on tour excursion development, for monuments of women in local history and to ensure that the experience is educational, engaging, and respectful, a set of best approaches is presented below, to select the most suitable for each country.

The first phase of excursion will take place at a pilot phase with 160 persons in total (at least in the pilot excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. Following to the excursion, all partners will collect the feedback, make the necessary changes, and then prepare another excursión, the final one.

Final excursion will involve 160 persons in total (at least in the excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. At the end a total of 320 participants (as a minimum), at least half of the total (160) must be young people.

The participants of the excursions will consist of young people and educators, trainers and academics:

- young people, boys, and girls
- young people active in local community groups such as Municipalities' Youth Councils
- students from the fields of History
- students from the fields of Gender Studies
- youth experts
- youth organizations
- Academics from the fields of History and Gender Studies
- Teachers and educators
- Teachers, and women and human rights organizations experts/activists

Each partner will create different and specific activities for the excursions organized in their city, for the pilots and the final ones. A set of general guidelines are presented below and each partner will analyse and formulate the topics of the guidelines with additions in the excursion descriptions, based on each country specifics.

The target audience for the tour guide guidelines is:

- A. touristic offices and educators.
- B. Small groups (independent excursions)

This document outlines Infinite Opportunities Association's plan to organize a gamified tour around Sofia in the form of a treasure hunt, in which groups will have the opportunity to explore the history of prominent women in the city. At different locations of the tour various questions are available to promote knowledge and curiosity within the group. For best results the group size should be around 20 people maximum.

2. Guidelines to develop a physical excursion

LEVEL 1: How to create a unique tour.

1. Define Objectives:

General Objective:

Using an interactive educational experience to highlight and give more visibility to the women of Sofia with their remarkable contributions throughout the history of the city.

Specific objectives:

- To create a historical cultural route through the center of Sofia including various places of memory related to Bulgarian women;
- To implement a city tour, visiting locations that emphasize on the contributions of women who have stood out throughout history with their values and deeds;
- To encourage cultural interest in learning about the female figures, related to the history of the city of Sofia;
- To present to the visitors a different view of the city – one that is focused on different women's issues, to place them in a historical and social context, within the framework of urban development and civil society;
- To provide information on feminism, the women's rights movement and its prominent figures.

2. Define the thematic of the excursion:

This tour focuses on the social activation and inclusion of Bulgarian women in the 20th century. All chosen locations are in one way or another related to this theme as it was central to the development of the Bulgarian Feminist movement at the time.

3. Recommend a rich educational content for each woman presented:

A detailed information sheet about each of the places of memory, related to women in Sofia and their achievements and contributions, together with historical facts about them and the times they lived in:

CITY, COUNTRY:	Sofia, Bulgaria
LOCATION NUMBER:	1
LOCATION:	Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski"
WOMAN:	Elizaveta Karamikhailova
INFORMATION:	<p>Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski" is a state research university in Sofia, Bulgaria. It is the oldest higher education institution in the country. The university's main building was built between 1924 and 1934 with the financial support of the brothers Evlogy and Hristo Georgievi. Classes began modestly and without noise on 1 October 1888. This is the birth date of the Bulgarian university education - only 10 years after the country's liberation.</p> <p>The university opened its doors with only eight professors who, although few in number and almost all graduates from abroad, still managed to bring the spirit of higher education from different European countries all the way to Sofia. At the beginning, there were 43 students, only men. The first women were admitted in 1901, after many years of petitioning at the National Assembly. Thus, the nation's potential for scientific innovation and the development of Bulgarian science in general were significantly increased.</p> <p>Today, Bulgaria is at the forefront in Europe regarding the number of women scientists in various scientific institutes. One of these eminent women is Elizaveta Karamihailova - the first Bulgarian nuclear physicist, the first woman habilitated lecturer at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski and one of the founders of the Department of Atomic Physics at the University. You can find out more about her in the next location.</p>

LOCATION NUMBER:	2
LOCATION:	Elizaveta Karamihailova's Memorial plaque
WOMAN:	Elizaveta Karamihailova (1897-1968)
INFORMATION:	<p>Elizaveta Karamihailova (1897-1968) was the first woman nuclear physicist in Bulgaria. She created the first practical courses in elementary particle physics and became the first woman professor in the country.</p> <p>Elizaveta began her academic career by enrolling in the prestigious First Sofia Girls' High School (more about this - in the next locations), where her teachers, active participants in the feminist movement, introduced her to the feminist ideas. After achieving excellent results in her studies, in 1917 she went to Vienna to study at the University of Vienna. She chose to study electrical and radio engineering, as these were the only courses open to women at that institution at the time. Her research on gamma rays and polonium is still relevant today and is considered a significant advance in modern physics.</p> <p>In 1923, Elizaveta was invited to join the study of the transmutation of atoms using alpha rays, which was at that time a cutting-edge area of nuclear physics. At the Institute for Radium Research, where she worked together with renowned physicists, she contributed significantly to the development of this field. Elizaveta graduated with a PhD in physics and mathematics in Vienna. Although she and her colleague Marietta Blau were on the verge of discovering neutrons, the delay in publishing their results prevented them from receiving the recognition they deserved.</p> <p>Elizaveta's success motivated her to return to Bulgaria in order to contribute to the development of the scientific community. Despite facing challenges such as lack of support and equipment, as well as blatant sexism from her male colleagues, she continued to persevere. She converted her office into a laboratory to provide her students with hands-on training in modern scientific methods. In 1939, after many years of efforts,</p>

	<p>she was finally appointed full associate professor of experimental atomic physics at Sofia University.</p> <p>In 1945, Elizaveta became head of the newly established Department of Atomic Physics at the university, marking another milestone in her remarkable career. Although she held the post of head of the department until 1955, after 1944 her status as a "credible" scientist was called into question because of her "bourgeois background" and her links with scientists behind the Iron Curtain. Consequently, she was expelled from the university. Elizaveta chose to donate all her belongings to the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, which, however, did not prevent the institution from imposing restrictions on her work until the 1980s.</p> <p>Her name rarely appears in any articles, which vaguely acknowledge, if only fleetingly, her contributions as a physicist, but completely ignore her role as a feminist and university lecturer. Despite this, Elizaveta's legacy remains as the first Bulgarian woman to achieve success in atomic physics to receive significant global recognition, challenging the notion that academia is exclusively reserved for male scientists.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER:	3
LOCATION:	Konstantsa Lyapcheva's Home
WOMAN:	Konstantsa Lyapcheva (1887-1944)
INFORMATION:	<p>Konstantsa Lyapcheva (1887-1944) was a socialite who engaged in charity work for underprivileged children (refugees, orphans, etc.).</p> <p>During the Balkan Wars (1912-1913), as a Sister of Charity, she helped wounded soldiers and refugees, and in peacetime she became a protector of the Bulgarian children. For her humanitarian deeds she was awarded the Grand Cross of the Bulgarian Red Cross and the Ladies' Order of Civil Merit of Tsar Boris III.</p>

	<p>In the 1930s, Konstantsa became the first woman to actively engage in issues such as human trafficking, domestic violence, and child protection. Until the very end, she was president of the Union for the Protection of Children in Bulgaria. She was a member of almost all other charities in Sofia, in many of them as part of the governing body. There was no area of social welfare in which she was not involved. Thanks to Konstantsa, the activities of raising and educating children received legislative protection, and motherhood was recognized as an extremely important social function. It was her own initiative that 1 June was celebrated as Children's Day for the first time in 1927. She founded the country's first shelters for children in distress, training centers for social workers, summer camps and playgrounds.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER:	4
LOCATION:	National Assembly of the Republic of Bulgaria
WOMAN:	None (General Women's Rights in Bulgaria)
INFORMATION:	<p>On January 15, 1938, Bulgarian women were granted the legal right to vote, the culmination of a long and complex journey towards women's suffrage in the country. The first step was taken in 1909 with the passing of the National Education Act, which for the first time granted women the right to serve on school boards, although they were not allowed to participate in elections. This formal and limited concession failed to produce tangible results, as men continued to favor predominantly male candidates for positions on the boards, keeping women away from the polls.</p> <p>In 1937, a partial victory was achieved when "women mothers by lawful marriage" were allowed to vote in local elections, although they remained ineligible to run. Eventually, on 15 January 1938, Bulgarian women gained the legal right to vote in parliamentary elections, albeit limited to women over 21 who were married, divorced or widowed. This restriction was open and clear - it excluded young, educated and free women, many</p>

	<p>of whom were studying abroad or had established themselves as intellectuals, from the electoral process.</p> <p>It was not until 1944 that women in Bulgaria received equal voting rights, and in 1945, during the 26th session of the National Assembly, the first 16 women were elected as deputies. After the elections to the 49th National Assembly, the 57 women included in it accounted for only 23.8% representation. According to the Inter-Parliamentary Union, the average percentage of women's representation in parliament worldwide is 26.5%, and in the same ranking, Bulgaria ranks 97th for women's participation in parliament.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER:	5
LOCATION:	Elena Markova-Bosilkova's Home
WOMAN:	Elena Markova-Bosilkova (1894-1971)
INFORMATION:	Elena Markova-Bosilkova (1894-1971) was the first Bulgarian architect.

LOCATION NUMBER:	6
LOCATION:	First Sofia State Girls High School (now, 7th Secondary School "Sveti Sedmochiselnitsi") & Anastasia Golovina's Workplace
WOMAN:	Dr. Anastasia Golovina (1850 - 1933)
INFORMATION:	7 Secondary School "St. Sedmochislenitsi" was originally founded in 1879 by a special decree of the Minister of Education Marin Drinov as the First Sofia State Girls' High School. The history of girls' secondary education in Bulgaria began here. Thirsty for knowledge, girls arrived from all over the country - Koprivshtitsa, Kalofer, Stara Zagora, Prilep, Pirdop, Pleven, Varna, etc., which in turn necessitated the opening of a boarding school. In 1882-1883, with the opening of a special pedagogical class, the gymnasium reached its full development. The foundations of the present building on Tsar Shishman street were laid on 24 April

1924. Designed by Mara Zaharieva, herself a graduate of the high school and one of the first female architects in the country, it managed to incorporate many of the European architectural examples of the era.

Among the teachers at the high school are names like Mara Belcheva, Ekaterina Karavelova and Elisaveta Konsolova-Vazova (about them - in the next locations). Among its graduates are a large number of Bulgarian intellectuals and artists such as Yana Yazova, Stoyanka Mutafova, Blaga Dimitrova, Elizaveta Bagryana, Vera Mutafchieva, Hristina Morfova, Tatyana Lazova and others.

Dr. Anastasia Golovina (1850 - 1933) worked at the First Sofia State Girls' High School as a doctor. She was the first Bulgarian doctor to graduate with a doctorate and the first Bulgarian female doctor.

She devoted her life to medicine and at a very young age went to study in Zurich, Switzerland. This decision was unusual given the extremely low number of women among medical students throughout Europe at the time. Anastasia continued her studies in Paris and on 27 December 1878 graduated with a brilliantly defended doctoral thesis. Before her, only five women had graduated as doctors from the Faculty of Medicine in Paris.

In 1879 she returned to newly liberated Bulgaria. At that time Anastasia was the first Bulgarian woman with a university degree and the first Bulgarian woman doctor.

Her innovations in Bulgaria related to the autopsy of the deceased to specify and confirm the cause of death. Anastasia was also the author of numerous scientific and popular articles in the field of medicine published in Bulgarian and foreign journals and was among the founders of the Physico-medical Society, the first association of physicians in Bulgaria. She took part in the Balkan wars and the World War I as a doctor in Varna.

Later, Anastasia became the first Bulgarian psychiatrist and one of the founders of Bulgarian balneotherapy and physiotherapy, introducing walks for the patients outside the psychiatric ward and improving the conditions of stay.

LOCATION NUMBER:	7
LOCATION:	Ekaterina Karavelova's Grave
WOMAN:	Ekaterina Karavelova (1860-1947)
INFORMATION:	<p>Ekaterina Karavelova (1860-1947) was a famous educator, translator, writer, publicist, suffragist and women's rights activist. She also played an active role in protecting Bulgaria's Jewish population from deportation to concentration camps during World War II. Ekaterina became the long-time president of the Union of Bulgarian Women Writers, which she initiated, and represented Bulgaria at the Fourth Congress of the International Women's League for Peace and Freedom in 1924 in Washington, DC. She was the founder of the cultural women's organization "Maika" and its chairwoman in 1899-1929. Active as a teacher, Ekaterina took an early part in the debate on women's education and the status of teachers. (Continues in the next location)</p>

LOCATION NUMBER:	8
LOCATION:	Ekaterina Karavelova's Memorial plaque
WOMAN:	Ekaterina Karavelova (1860-1947)
INFORMATION:	<p>(Continues from the previous location)</p> <p>In addition, Ekaterina made a huge contribution to the development of the women's movement in Bulgaria and to the affirmation of the role of women in society. She was one of the founders of the Bulgarian Women's Union in 1901 and its president from 1915 to 1925. Karavelova led "Maika" to the establishment of the first girls' trade school in Bulgaria "Maria Luisa".</p>

LOCATION NUMBER:	9
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LOCATION:	Elisaveta Bagryana's Memorial plaque
WOMAN:	Elisaveta Bagryana (1893-1991)
INFORMATION:	<p>Elisaveta Bagryana (1893-1991) was a prominent Bulgarian poet who lived most of her life in Sofia. She is regarded as one of the most significant Bulgarian poets, often referred to as 'the first lady of Bulgarian women's literature'. Known both for her lyrics and for her unconventional views on the role of women in society, the poet was an active figure in literary and social life in Bulgaria in the 1920s. Bagryana collaborated in various media - "The Woman's Herald", "Lyk" newspaper, "Contemporary", "Zlatorog", "Izkustvo" magazines, etc., and published her first book - "The Eternal and the Holy" in 1927. Elisaveta was nominated three times for the Nobel Prize in Literature and made a significant contribution to the country's literary heritage.</p> <p>Somewhat arguing for her unconventional behaviour, she confronted the idea of women according to patriarchal norms and interpreted the problem of freedom of choice and the will of a person to assert herself in a different way. Other leading themes in Bagryana's work are love, travel, loneliness and memories.</p> <p>Her poems have been translated into 30 languages and published in France, Greece, Czechoslovakia, Yugoslavia, Romania, Italy, Sweden, Poland, etc. Her work "The White Fence" was written for the 50th anniversary of the First Sofia State Girls' High School in 1929 (more information about the school - in the previous location).</p>

LOCATION NUMBER:	10
LOCATION:	Yana Yazova's Memorial plaque
WOMAN:	Yana Yazova (1912-1974)
INFORMATION:	Yana Yazova (1912-1974) was a 20th century writer and intellectual. Her poetry has been translated into Esperanto,

	<p>Czech, Serbian and Ukrainian. She traveled widely in Europe and the Middle East and wrote about her travels.</p> <p>After the communist regime she was not printed, published or invited to literary readings. In almost complete solitude, she created the trilogy "Balkans", including the novels "Levski", "Benkovski" and "Shipka" - a colossal work for which she spent years in libraries and archives, wandering in monasteries. Her historical novel "Alexander the Great", the trilogy "Balkans" and the anti-communist novel "The Salt Bay" were published after her death.</p> <p>Yana Yazova died under circumstances that remain unclear to this day. The last sign that she was alive is her note in a notebook dated 19 May 1974. Her body was discovered in her home in late July. She was buried on 9 August in the Central Sofia Cemetery. Yana Yazova's state file was destroyed.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER:	11
LOCATION:	Bulgarian Womens' Union building and Anna Karima's workplace
WOMAN:	Anna Karima (1871-1949)
INFORMATION:	<p>The Bulgarian Women's Union was a women's rights organization, active in Bulgaria from 1901 to 1944. In 1901 the association was founded by Vela Blagoeva, Ekaterina Karavelova, Anna Karima, Kina Konova, Julia Malinova and Zheni Pateva. The organization united the 27 local women's associations established in Bulgaria since 1878. It was founded in response to restrictions on women's education and access to university studies in the 1890s.</p> <p>Anna Karima (1871-1949) was a writer, translator, editor and journalist, suffragist and women's rights activist. In 1897 she founded the Women's Educational Association "Consciousness", through which Anna, with her persistent letters to the government, managed to convince it in 1901 to allow women to study at university. Anna became the first president of the</p>

	<p>Bulgarian Women's Union and organized the first congress of feminist organizations.</p> <p>Throughout her life, she was constantly engaged in translating and writing her own material, all of it devoted to women's issues - from the education of children, to opposition to arranged marriages, to the free expression of emotions - her works challenged the traditional notions of the time, combating stereotypes and influencing attitudes towards women.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER:	12
LOCATION:	Teodora Peykova's Workplace
WOMAN:	Teodora Peykova (1892-1972)
INFORMATION:	<p>Teodora Peykova (1892-1972) was a writer, editor and social activist, founder of the women's magazine Economy and Household, which was published for 25 years. Through the magazine, Teodora spread European tendencies and ideas throughout the country and used it to introduce women to various social problems or inventions made by other women, to offer recipes and medical advice, weight-loss diets, press reviews, family advice, child-rearing tips, fashion, historical events, gymnastics, reports from Paris and other cities, advertisements, sewing, embroidery, needlework courses, and more.</p> <p>She also became the first Bulgarian woman to teach herself to drive her husband's car. During socialism, the Economy and Household magazine was declared bourgeois and banned, the complicated and beautiful European dishes and eating habits were replaced by simple and "folk" ones, and Teodora Peykova sank into oblivion.</p>

LOCATION NUMBER:	13
LOCATION:	Mara Belcheva's Home

WOMAN:	Mara Belcheva (1868-1937)
INFORMATION:	Mara Belcheva (1868-1937) was a poet, teacher, translator and philologist. She published three collections of poetry, Steps on the Threshold, 1918, Sonnets, 1926, and Selected Songs, 1931. In 1925, Mara published a biography of her late partner, the poet Pencho Slaveykov. She also translated Friedrich Nietzsche's Thus Spake Zarathustra and Gerhart Hauptmann's Die versunkene Glocke into Bulgarian.

LOCATION NUMBER:	14
LOCATION:	Dimitrana Ivanova's Home
WOMAN:	Dimitrana Ivanova (1881-1960)
INFORMATION:	<p>Dimitrana Ivanova (1881-1960) was a Bulgarian educational reformer, suffragist and women's rights activist. She was president of the Bulgarian Women's Union from 1926 to 1944. From 1928 she published and edited the monthly magazine "The Woman" (1929-1931), which dealt with the legal aspects of women's subordinate position. Dimitrana collaborated with many newspapers on issues related to women's lives and futures.</p> <p>Throughout her life she fought for gender equality in education, and for the right of women lawyers to practice their profession as lawyers and judges. After a long struggle, she became one of the first Bulgarian women to have this right recognized. Dimitrana's big dream is that Bulgarian women should have the right to vote and be equal in different spheres of life. Thanks to many years of activism and with the help of Queen Joanna, a new electoral law was promulgated in January 1938, partially guaranteeing this right to married, divorced or widowed women.</p>

4. Define a compelling excursion tour content:

Additional visual materials selected to be shared with the participants in the tour:

5. Tour Excursion Planning:

This tour is organized based on the geographical proximity of all places of memory, listed above. It's planned for a total duration of 90 minutes, including all discussions as well. The first location chosen (Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski") is a good meeting point for the group to gather as it's a well-known, easily reachable and well connected by public transport place in the city center and the sidewalk in front of the main entrance with the 2 statues is spacious enough to allow bigger groups to meet without any disturbance to the public. In case of any special events occurring at the proposed meeting place, an adequate substitute can be chosen instead among the many available options around the location (parks, underpass, etc.). After finishing the tour, the participants can easily reach the park of the National Palace of Culture (1 minute away) as a big open space with benches to share their observations and provide feedback.

Anyone implementing the tour should have in mind that Sofia city's infrastructure is often not suited for people with reduced mobility. However, the proposed route is spread onto a mostly flat part of Sofia center and involves one underpass with a ramp after location 3.

LEVEL 2: How to implement an exciting tour.

1. Add Interactive Elements to excursion tour:

For this tour we've prepared a set of questions that aim to encourage knowledge retention and inspire curiosity towards women's impact in the history of different cities into the participants. The questions can be asked throughout the tour, for example after visiting a specific location. Some of the women, mention above, are related to more than one place of memory, listed in this document. This could present a good opportunity to remind the participants about the specific figure and ask some of the questions, thus, increasing interactivity and creating more mental links between the locations.

Questions:

1. In which year did women begin to attend University in Bulgaria?

A. 1901

B. 1888

C. 1903

2. Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski" is the:

A. Biggest higher education institution in Bulgaria

B. Oldest higher education institution in Bulgaria

C. Most modern higher education institution in Bulgaria

D. All the above

3. Elizaveta Karamihailova was:

A. The first woman nuclear physicist in Bulgaria

B. The head of the Department of Atomic Physics at the Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski"

C. An associate professor of experimental atomic physics at Sofia University

D. The first woman professor in the country

E. All the above

4. While studying at the University of Vienna, Elizaveta Karamihailova researched:

A. uranium

B. radio signals transmission

C. gamma rays and polonium

5. The Bulgarian Academy of Sciences treated Elizaveta as:

A. A non-credible scientist

B. A renowned scientist in her field

C. A bourgeois

6. Konstantsa Lyapcheva was actively engaged with the following topic:

A. Human trafficking

B. Domestic violence

C. Child protection

D. All the above

7. Which awards did Konstantsa Lyapcheva receive throughout her lifetime?

A. Grand Cross of the Bulgarian Red Cross

B. Nobel Peace Prize

C. Ladies' Order of Civil Merit of Tsar Boris III

D. All the above

8. When were Bulgarian women granted equal voting rights?

A. 1944

B. 1945

C. 1937

9. From 15 January 1938 onwards which Bulgarian women gained the legal right to vote in parliamentary elections?

A. Women over 21 who were married, divorced or widowed

B. Women over 18 who were mothers

C. Women with a University degree

10. How many women were elected as deputies during the 26th session of the National Assembly?

A. 3

B. 16

C. 38

11. Who was the architect of the First Sofia Girls' High School building?

A. Elena Markova-Bosilkova

B. Mara Zaharieva

C. Elisaveta Konsolova-Vazova

12. Famous graduates of First Sofia Girls' High School are:

A. Elizaveta Karamihailova and Mara Zaharieva

- B. Yana Yazova and Elizaveta Bagryana
- C. Stoyanka Mutafova and Blaga Dimitrova

D. All the above

13. Dr. Anastasia Golovina became:

- A. The first Bulgarian doctor to graduate with a doctorate
- B. The first Bulgarian female doctor
- C. One of the first 6 women graduates of the Faculty of Medicine in Paris
- D. The first Bulgarian psychiatrist

E. All the above

14. Which wars did Anastasia take part in as a medic?

A. World War I

B. World War II

C. Balkan wars

15. Throughout her life Dr. Anastasia Golovina introduced the following medical innovations in Bulgaria:

- A. Balneotherapy and physiotherapy
- B. Autopsy of the deceased to specify and confirm the cause of death
- C. Walks for the patients outside the psychiatric ward

D. All the above

16. What is Ekaterina Karavelova famous for:

A. It was her own initiative that 1 June was celebrated as Children's Day for the first time in 1927

B. She played an active role in protecting Bulgaria's Jewish population from deportation to concentration camps during World War II

C. She was nominated 3 times for a Nobel Prize in Literature

D. All the above

17. Ekaterina Karavelova was:

A. One of the founders of the Bulgarian Women's Union in 1901

B. A long-time president of the Union of Bulgarian Women Writers

C. An educator, translator, writer, publicist, suffragist and women's rights activist

D. All the above

18. Elisaveta Bagryana was:

A. Nominated three times for the Nobel Prize in Literature

B. Often referred to as 'the best among all Bulgarian women poets'

C. An renowned translator who knew 7 languages

19. Elisaveta's works revolve around the central topics of:

A. confronting the idea of women according to patriarchal norms

B. the problem of freedom of choice and the will of a person

C. love, travel, loneliness and memories

D. All the above

20. Yana Yazova did the following:

A. Devoted years of her life in almost complete solitude to create the trilogy "Balkans"

B. Traveled widely in Europe and the Middle East and wrote about her travels

C. Was published in various magazines: "The Woman's Herald", "Lyk", "Contemporary", "Zlatorog", "Izkustvo"

D. All the above

21. The Bulgarian Women's Union:

A. was founded by Vela Blagoeva, Ekaterina Karavelova, Anna Karima

B. united the 27 local women's associations

C. was active in Bulgaria from 1901 to 1944

D. All the above

22. Why was The Bulgarian Women's Union founded:

A. To establish a matriarchy in Bulgaria

B. To support women in their professional fulfillment

C. To fight the restrictions on women's education and access to university studies in the 1890s

23. Whose letters managed to convince the government in 1901 to allow women to study at university?

A. Ekaterina Karavelova

B. Anna Karima

C. Konstantsa Lyapcheva

D. All the above

24. Anna Karima became:

- A. A writer, translator, editor and journalist, suffragist and women's rights activist**
- B. The first president of the Bulgarian Women's Union**
- C. The first woman to graduate from Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"
- D. All the above

25. The works of Anna Karima were devoted to:

- A. The education of children**
- B. The approval of arranged marriages
- C. Combating stereotypes and influencing attitudes towards women**
- D. All the above

26. What materials and topics were included in Economy and Household magazine?

- A. Technical literature regarding cheap household repairs
- B. Poetry written by women
- C. Inventions made by women**
- D. All the above

27. Teodora Peykova became:

- A. The founder of the women's magazine Economy and Household
- B. A writer, editor and social activist
- C. The first Bulgarian woman to teach herself to drive
- D. All the above**

28. Mara Belcheva translated:

- A. Her late partner, the poet Pencho Slaveykov's works into German
- B. Friedrich Nietzsche's Thus Spake Zarathustra into Bulgarian**
- C. Gerhart Hauptmann's Die versunkene Glocke into Bulgarian**
- D. All the above

29. Dimitrana Ivanova was:

- A. The president of the Bulgarian Women's Union from 1926 to 1944**
- B. The first president of the Bulgarian Women's Union
- C. The founder of the women's magazine Economy and Household

30. What did Dimitrana fight for throughout her life?

- A. Equal voting rights for Bulgarian women
- B. Gender equality in education
- C. The right of women lawyers to practice their profession
- D. All the above**

In case the HerStory mobile app, developed through the project's timeline, is ready for use during the tour pilot phase, it will be incorporated as well. For the time being, we will use the interactive questions prepared and the supporting audiovisual material at the locations to underline the prominent women's presence.

2. Verify accessibility and provide necessary information:

When organizing the specific tour, we will take into consideration any needs of the individuals with reduced mobility or of advanced age. In such cases, parts of the route can be adapted, for example, by shortening the tour to 60 minutes (skipping the last and slightly distant location) if needed and including more breaks so that everyone is able to participate fully. We

are prepared to include enough photographs and additional digital materials of the locations in order to provide a diverse and engaging tour for all.

No culturally sensitive information is included in the planned tour. IOA's team members, leading the group, are able to communicate in English in case any participants do not have a strong command of Bulgarian.

3. Receive Feedback and Improvement:

After finishing the tour at location 14, the participants will be asked to complete the HerStory questionnaire to provide valuable feedback for us. They will have the opportunity to share any suggestions for improvement, comments, questions, or concerns they may have regarding the physical excursion. This feedback will help us make any necessary improvements to enhance future experiences as well as provide data on participant involvement and satisfaction with the implemented activity.

Additionally, reminders will be sent in the days following the tour to encourage participants to respond to the questionnaire using the email address provided during registration. Furthermore, the European Commission survey will be used for project purposes.

4. Engage Locals through Collaborations:

IOA has identified the following potential collaborators: 170 school "Vasil Levski", Novi Iskar, due to their extensive teaching of managing tour guides/excursions, the Bulgarian Fund for Women, Sofia Free Tours, the National Tourist Office.

LEVEL 3: Generic guidelines for individual and self-guided tours.

5. Enable the customization of excursions:

The pilot tours within the HerStory project are scheduled to occur between April and June 2024. This activity aims to highlight the significant contributions made by women in the city. Possible international day that can serve as beneficial to hold the tour on can be 24 June (International Day for Women in Diplomacy).

Regarding the final tours of the project, they can be organized around the following key dates: 18 September (International Equal Pay Day) or October 11 (International Day of the Girl Child).

6. Develop options for Training Guides or/and self-guided tours:

In essence, the HerStory project offers city tours in Sofia designed as treasure hunts. The main aim is to explore the history of prominent women who have made significant contributions to the city and to other women's wellbeing. During the tour, the participants will encounter various questions posed by the guide. Correct answers unlock insights into each landmark location, guiding the group to the next destination. This approach is intended to raise awareness of influential women from various fields, blending gamification elements with interactive participation.

Adapting the experience for a self-guided tour provides participants with the flexibility to explore the city at their own pace while engaging interactively with the history of distinguished women in Sofia. For those opting for a self-guided tour, we recommend the following suggestions:

1. Research and Knowledge.

Thoroughly research the history of various prominent women associated with the city of Sofia. This includes understanding both the times they lived in and their contributions, achievements, and significance within various fields such as politics, arts, sciences, and social activism.

2. Identify Points of Interest (optional).

You could identify additional key landmarks, buildings, monuments, and locations associated with the women being highlighted and, thus, expand your own HerStory tour. Possible locations could include birthplaces, residences, workplaces, memorials, and sites of significant events related to their lives.

3. Craft Engaging Narratives.

Prepare engaging narratives and anecdotes about each prominent woman to share with tour participants. Incorporate interesting facts, personal stories, and historical context to bring their stories to life.

4. Create an informative resource (a brochure or a leaflet).

To present the 14 different current locations related to prominent women throughout Sofia's history, you can develop a complete document with all the necessary information. This material should provide details about each woman and their respective locations within the city. The leaflet should also include information regarding the specific landmark as well as a description of each location and its significance to provide context for the participants.

5. Provide Clear Directions.

Ensure that the tour route is clearly marked and easy to follow. Include directions, maps, and navigation tips to help participants navigate between different points of interest.

6. Offer Multimedia Resources.

Enhance the tour experience by incorporating multimedia resources such as photographs, videos, audio recordings or guides, podcasts, mobile apps and digital presentations. These can help provide visual and auditory context to complement the guide's narration. Incorporate multimedia resources such as that participants can access while exploring the tour route.

7. Utilize the online HerStory map.

This combination of the HerStory map together with the planned leaflet allows the participants to verify points of interest using both the map and accompanying images, links and information. This approach offers clear visual guidance, making it easier for participants to identify each landmark during their self-guided exploration as well as enhances the self-guided tour experience.

8. Incorporate Technology.

Additionally, you could also leverage technology such as augmented reality (AR) or virtual reality (VR) to enhance the tour experience. Offer virtual tours or immersive experiences that allow participants to visualize historical scenes and locations associated with prominent women.

9. Create an interactive engagement.

With the help of an interactive questionnaire the participants will be able to test their own knowledge during the self-guided tour. It should cover topics related to the history of the

prominent women above and the sites the participants visit. You can also use the questions provided in this document. Incorporating various interactive elements into the tour, such as quizzes, QR codes and treasure hunts, will actively engage participants and encourage their participation as they explore the tour route.

10. Encourage Exploration.

Encourage participants to explore beyond the designated tour route and discover additional sites and stories related to prominent women in Sofia. Provide suggestions for further exploration and discovery.

11. Share Resources for Further Learning.

Offer resources for participants to continue learning about the women featured in the tour, such as recommended reading lists, online archives, or local events and exhibitions.

12. Promote Accessibility.

Ensure that the tour materials and resources are accessible to all participants, including those with disabilities or special needs. Provide alternative formats, translations, or accommodations to make the tour inclusive and accessible to a diverse audience.

By following these recommendations, you can create an informative, engaging, and memorable experience for participants exploring the rich history of prominent women in Sofia.

Extra tips

Having a QR Code printed to go to the local map of the city, so people can follow the tour or access to the guidelines to make the tour in an educational way.

2. Documentation and templates

The deliverables of WP4 activities are presented below.

D4.1 HerStory Map pilot implementation

- **Invitation/ agenda/ program:** A template will be shared by KEAN.
- **Signed attendance list**
- **Minutes/ report (tbd)**
- **Other evidence** (in case of pictures we need consent forms)